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Effect Of Rational-Emotive And Cognitive Behaviour Therapies On Self-esteem And Academic Performance Of Probating Students In Colleges Of Education In Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigated the Effect of rational-emotive and cognitive behaviour therapies on self-esteem and academic performance of probating students in colleges of education in Taraba State, Nigeria. four research questions guided the study and four research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted quasi-experimental design of randomized, pre-test and post-test. The population of the study was 124 probating students from the two Colleges of education in the state. The sample size for the study is forty (40) participants purposively selected. An adapted instrument was used for the study titled Self Esteem Questionnaire (SEQ). The SEQ was duly validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Taraba State University, Jalingo. The reliability of the SEQ was obtained using Cronbach-Alpha it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.849. Descriptive statistics of mean, and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while a paired samples t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that rational-emotive and cognitive behaviour therapies improved self-esteem and academic performance of probating students in colleges of education in Taraba State, it was also found that rational-emotive is more effective on Goal setting while cognitive behaviour therapy is more effective on Self-acceptance of probating students from the two Colleges of education. It was recommended that counsellors in colleges of education should use Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy when improving students self-esteem (Goal setting) while Counsellors should also be given the opportunity to give or expose students to counselling sessions designed to improve their self-concept, mental health and update their total well-being. Workshops and seminars in counselling should be organized by the ministry of education often in order to acquaint both the students and staff on how to help those students to reintegrate.

Keywords: Rational-Emotive Cognitive Behaviour Therapy Self-Esteem Academic Performance Probating Students and Colleges Of Education.

INTRODUCTION

Man is fully aware that he has a 'self, and he also has the ability to think. In view of this consciousness of man, the need for man to think about himself and the events that influence him becomes inevitable. The awareness of self and events that influence it makes choices and decisions unavoidable at every moment.

The ability to make choices and take decisions implies that man is free, because man is free; the existentialists believe that man is what he makes of himself (Otta, 2016). Therefore, the way one views and feels about oneself has a deep effect on how the individual lives. Therefore, the proverb, "As a man thinks in his heart, so is he," not only refers to a person's entire existence but also to every situation and scenario in his life (Allen, 2022). An individual therefore is literally what he thinks; his character and achievement being the complete sum of all his thoughts.

An individual's degree of performance in any given task and his relationships with others are significantly influenced by his self-perception and self-worth. This is known as "self-esteem" in psychology. Rosenberg (2015) further defined the term "self-esteem" as one's attitude, whether positive or negative, toward oneself. McLeod (2018) characterizes self-esteem as a constant, self-referential assessment of one's own traits, skills, and behavior. Harter (2018) defines self-esteem as an individual's total evaluation of their own worth. Juth, Smyth, and Santuzzi (2018) define self-esteem as an individual's evaluation of their own aptitudes, competencies, and general characteristics that impact and promote certain mental processes and behaviors in them.

Dedmond (2022) thought of self-esteem as the complex mix of sentiments about oneself that fuels motivation, shapes attitudes, and directs behavior. As to Khan (2022), self-esteem is a somewhat constant positive or negative feeling about oneself that might change based on how individuals perceive and analyze their daily achievements and setbacks. Furthermore, from the latter part of the 20th century, researchers have studied the psychological notion of self-Esteem. It is a comprehensive theoretical framework that is widely regarded as a key marker of mental well-being and adaptive human functioning. Research studies have considered self-esteem to arise as a function of the individual's interaction with the social environment. According to James (2019), individuals' perceptions of themselves are shaped by their relationships with other people. According to him, a person's "success (to) pretensions" ratio, or the ratio of their achievements to failures in significant life areas, determines their level of self-esteem. From a theoretical and methodological standpoint, social psychologists may still apply many of James' foundational concepts. Academics highlight how social roles, norms, symbols, and categories as well as people's shared values all contribute to the social construction of the self through contact (Mead 2019 & Vygotsky (2019).

Academic performance has been known to be influenced by several factors. One of such factors is the individual's Self-Esteem. Self-Esteem, as defined by Robbins and Franken (2017), is a person's overall sense of self-worth, which encompasses beliefs about their abilities, values, and attributes. It is a multidimensional construct that affects various aspects of human functioning, including cognitive, emotional, motivational, and social processes. According to Robbins and Franken, Self-Esteem plays a crucial role in shaping an individual's identity, well-being, and relationships.

Similarly, Wigfield and Karpathian (2015) in their study on understanding indicators related to academic performance, reported five academic-related indicators that they believe could have positive or negative effect on the individual. These indicators include educational expectations, number of books read, academic efficacy, self-reported grades and parent's involvement. These academic-related indicators as stated above are more of personal opinions and evaluation that the individual holds about self. When these opinions and self-evaluations are negative, the individual may encounter persistent academic difficulties. Hence, the need for intervention. Where these opinions and evaluations are positive, they enhance academic performance and where they are negative; the individual's academic performance is negatively influenced.

Goal setting can have a positive impact on an individual's self-esteem and academic performance, especially for probationary students who may be struggling academically or experiencing personal difficulties. Incorporating goal setting into the academic support provided to probationary students can positively impact their motivation, self-esteem, time management, resilience, and academic performance. By helping these students develop the skills and mindset necessary for success, educators and administrators can facilitate their transition from probationary status to good standing and support their long-term academic and professional aspirations. Here are some ways in which goal setting can benefit probationary students, along with some citations to support each point: Increased motivation, Improved

self-esteem, Enhanced resilience academic improvement. Finally, goal setting can directly contribute to improved academic performance among probationary students.

Self-acceptance refers to the extent to which an individual accepts and values themselves, including their strengths, weaknesses, and limitations. It is an important aspect of self-concept and can significantly impact an individual's self-esteem and academic performance. Research suggests that self-acceptance is positively correlated with self-esteem (Burbidge, 2021). Individuals with high self-acceptance tend to have higher self-esteem, whereas those with low self-acceptance tend to have lower self-esteem. This relationship makes sense, as self-acceptance reflects an individual's willingness to embrace and appreciate their entire self, including their perceived flaws and shortcomings.

Self-acceptance can also influence academic performance. Studies indicate that students with higher levels of self-acceptance tend to perform better academically (Hill, 2021). This may be because self-acceptance enables individuals to approach challenges with greater confidence and motivation, as they are less hindered by self-doubt and negative self-talk.

Rational-Emotive Therapy is based on the belief that emotional difficulties or problems have their roots in irrational thoughts and beliefs held by individuals. Rational-Emotive Therapy is formed on the basic assumption the assumption that people contribute to their own psychological problems as well as to specific symptoms by the way they interpret events and situations. The basic hypothesis of RET is that our emotion stem mainly from our beliefs, evaluations, interpretations and reactions to life situations. The therapeutic process teaches clients skills that give them the tools to identify and dispute irrational beliefs that have been acquired and self-constructed and are now maintained by self-indoctrination. Therapy is seen as an educational process. This study therefore presupposes that students are failing in their academics because of some irrational beliefs that affect academic performance negatively.

Rational-Emotive therapy is characterized by the therapists' communication (often highly dramatic) to the distortions in his/her thinking. The proponent of the therapy, Albert Ellis, feels that no one should be blamed for anything he or she does, but each person is responsible for both his and her negative and positive actions. Unhappiness results from within and can be controlled. Man is being able to intervene between environment input and emotional output and therefore is seen as having considerable control over what he thinks, feels and does. This therapy is much like a teaching technique and is, in fact great towards helping clients to change their bad thinking, behaviour and positively improved their self-esteem. According to Ellis (2015), the improvement and change of name was done to emphasize the fact that, it has always been cognitive, emotive and behavioral. Rational Emotive therapy aims at helping human beings achieve their basic goals and values. It is a method of solving emotional problems and also a technique whereby the clients are helped to maximize their self-actualizing tendencies and encouraging them to improve their self-esteem and assume responsibility for their own lives to become sensibly self-interested and self-directing. Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (RET) is a truly eclectic approach to therapy that employs a wide variety of cognitive, behavioural and emotive technique.

Cognitive behavioural therapy is considered to be one of the most rapid therapies when it comes to getting quick results. It is both brief and time-limited in comparison to other therapies. It is based upon the idea that our thoughts are not an external event like situation but one that is in fact actually the cause of our feelings and behaviour. According to the National Association of Cognitive Behavioural Therapies (2021), Cognitive Behavioural Therapy is based on the Cognitive model of emotional response. The model talks about individual feelings and behaviour stem from his/her thoughts, as opposed to external stimuli, it is a goal-oriented and problem-focused therapy, as a result of this, cognitive behavioural therapy focuses on the present and on the here and now rather than on a lengthy analysis of the individual's developmental history.

Behavioral protocol, such as Systematic Desensitization relies on deep muscle relaxation and pair relaxation to a graduated sequence of anxiety-provoking images. Counselling intervention particularly, anxiety and Mental Health counselling are essential in order to cut down excessive anxiety among test-anxious students. Through counselling, students experiencing test anxiety are helped to raise their ego domain, believe in themselves, be more assertive and resilient.

Statement of the Problem

It has been noted that students with low self-esteem such as low self-confidence, poor self-efficacy, low self-worth and poor self-respect tend to face lot of difficulties in the colleges of education in Taraba state and finds it difficult to relate with others and this affects their academic performance. Worst of all, these unfavorable outcomes serve to further solidify the poor self-perception and can send a person into a vicious cycle of progressively declining self-worth and more ineffective or even intentionally self-destructive conduct, which keeps students from overcoming their academic problems. Numerous issues, such as low self-esteem, low self-efficacy, low self-worth, low self-respect, and low self-confidence, might contribute to poor academic adjustment. These factors negatively impact the student's capacity to make decisions or evaluate their own academic performance.

This study is prompted by the researcher's experience with probating students during the researcher's service as a resource person at the Peacock College of Education Jalingo. From the records the researcher collected from the College authority, about ten percent of the students at each level of study between the year 2021 and 2022 academic session have a case of probation. This statistic is quite alarming and led to the researcher's interest in embarking on this study. During the researcher's counselling experience in the college, it was observed that, most if not all probating students counselled have low self-esteem on their ability to perform academically. The researcher also observed that probating students have low opinion about themselves. He also noticed that as a result of their low opinion about themselves, they tend to be pessimistic and lacking in strong self-esteem to cope with problems and disappointments. Low Self-Esteem has proven to impair and impede student's efforts to perform to the best of their ability in setting situation. Ohadike (2016), stated that success is particularly an important aspect in one's life and that it dictates the goal which one set for oneself, and whatever one achieves in life, depends on the value one places on such achievement. Low self-Esteem can be a hindrance in achieving this goal. This was confirmed by the result of a preliminary study conducted on a Self-Esteem questionnaire.

The data collected yielded a mean of 25.75 and a standard deviation of 2.87 indicating that the probating students have low Self-Esteem. In addition to low academic performance, the probating students also have low Self-Esteem which could be attributed to low academic performance. Though, there are indications that the students are likely to have low academic performance due to low Self-Esteem. This study is designed to ascertain the effect of Rational-Emotive Therapy on the Self-Esteem and academic performance of probating students. Hence, the problem of this study can be stated thus: What is the effect of Rational-Emotive Therapy on the Self-Esteem and academic performance of probating students?

It is in the light of the above issues that the studies of this nature emanate specifically, to investigate the effect of Rational-Emotive and Cognitive Behavioral therapies on the Self-Esteem and academic performance of probating students of colleges of Education, Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions serve as a guide for the investigation.

1. What is the effect of rational-emotive therapy on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State?
2. What is the effect of Cognitive behavioral Therapy on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State?
3. What is the effect of rational-emotive therapy on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State?
4. What is the effect of Cognitive behavioral Therapy on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State?

Research Hypotheses

The following theories were proposed and were tested at the significance level of 0.05.

H₀₁: Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy has no significant effect on the goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

H₀₂: Rational-Emotive Behaviour Therapy has no significant effect on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State

H₀₃: Cognitivebehavioral Therapy has no significant effect on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

H₀₄: Cognitive behavioral Therapy has no significant effect on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a Quasi-experimental research design. Quasi-experimental method helps to establish the effect of an intervention on a target population or the absence of an expected effect (White & Sabarwal, 2019), and it does not have the time and logistical constraints associated with true experimental design (Iortimah & Aligba, 2019). It is Quasi-experimental design because it is expected to establish the cause – effect relationship between the variables of study. The population of the study was 124 probating students from the two Colleges: Peacock College of Education Jalingo and College of Education Zing in Taraba Sate. The sample for this study comprised of 40 probating students purposively selected from the two colleges of education. Two set of adapted instruments were used for the study titled Self Esteem Questionnaire (SEQ). The instrument was duly validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education, Taraba State University, Jalingo. The reliability of the instrument was obtained using Cronbach-Alpha it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.849. The descriptive statistics of mean, and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while a paired samples t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Questions One: *What is the effect of Rational-Emotive Behaviour Therapy on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating of the Effect of Rational-Emotive Behaviour Therapy on Goal Setting of Probating Students of Colleges of Education

Goal Setting	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Gain	Std. Error Mean
Pre-test	20	1.96	0.30	1.01	0.66
Post-test	20	2.97	0.31		0.69

Table 1 shows pretest and post-test mean and standard deviation rating scores of probating student on goal setting in colleges of education in Taraba State. The mean pre-test score was 1.96, and standard deviation of 0.30, while the mean post-test score was 2.97 and standard deviation of 0.31. The mean gain of 1.01 implies that Rational-Emotive Behaviour Therapy is effective on goal setting among probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Research Question Two: *What is the effect of Rational-Emotive Behaviour Therapy on self-acceptance of probating students of college of education in Taraba State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating of the Effect of Rational-Emotive Behaviour Therapy on Self-acceptance of Probating Students of Colleges of Education

Self-acceptance	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Gain	Std. Error Mean
Pre-test	20	1.66	0.20	1.29	0.045
Post-test	20	2.95	0.30		0.068

Table 2. shows pretest and post-test mean and standard deviation rating scores of probating student on self-acceptance in colleges of education in Taraba State. The mean pre-test score was 1.66, and standard deviation of 0.20, while the mean post-test score was 2.95 and standard deviation of 0.30. The mean gain of 1.29 implies that Rational-Emotive Behaviour Therapy is effective on self-acceptance among probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Research Questions three: *What is the effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating of the Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on Goal Setting of Probating Students of Colleges of Education

Goal Setting	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Gain	Std. Error Mean
Pre-test	20	2.00	0.61	0.7	0.135
Post-test	20	2.74	0.16		0.035

Table 3 shows pretest and post-test mean and standard deviation rating scores of probating students on goal setting in colleges of education in Taraba State. The mean pre-test score was 2.00, and standard deviation of 0.61, while the mean post-test score was 2.74 and standard deviation of 0.16. The mean gain of 0.74 implies that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy is effective on goal setting among probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Research Questions Four: *What is the effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on self-acceptance of probating students of college of education in Taraba State?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation Rating of the Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on Self-acceptance of Probating Students of Colleges of Education

Self-acceptance	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Gain	Std. Error Mean
Pre-test	20	1.93	0.63	0.76	0.141
Post-test	20	2.69	0.17		0.038

Table 4 shows pretest and post-test mean and standard deviation rating scores of probating student on self-acceptance in colleges of education in Taraba State. The mean pre-test score was 1.93, and standard deviation of 0.63, while the mean post-test score was 2.69 and standard deviation of 0.17. The mean gain of 0.76 implies that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy is effective in improving self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Hypothesis One: Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy has no significant effect on the goal setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Table 5: Paired Sample t-test on Effect of Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy on Goal-setting of Probating Students of Colleges of Education in Taraba State

	Paired Differences		Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation		Lower	Upper			
Pre-test – Post-test	-1.01000	.40412	.09036	-1.19914	-.82086	-11.177	19	.000

Table 5 above presents results of paired samples t-test on effect of Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. The result show: $t(19) = -11.177, p < .001$. The result implies that there is a significant difference in means between pre-test and post-test on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education. The result implies that Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy has significant effect on goal-setting among probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy has no significant effect on the goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State is rejected.

Hypothesis Two: Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy has no significant effect on the self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Table 6: Paired Sample t-test on Effect of Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy on Self-acceptance of Probating Students of Colleges of Education in Taraba State

	Paired Differences							Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	Df	
				Lower	Upper			
Pre-test – Post-test	-1.28500	.41647	.09313	-1.47991	-1.09009	-13.799	19	.000

Table 6 presents results of paired samples t-test on effect of Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. The result show: $t(19) = -13.799, p < .001$. The result implies that there is a significant difference in means between pre-test and post-test on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education. The result implies that Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy has significant effect on self-acceptance among probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that Rational-Emotive behavior Therapy has no significant effect on the self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State is rejected.

Hypothesis three: Cognitive Behavioral Therapy has no significant effect on the goal-Setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Table 7: Paired Sample t-test on Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on Goal-setting of Probating Students of Colleges of Education in Taraba State

	Paired Differences							Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	Df	
				Lower	Upper			
Pre-test – Post-test	-.74000	.60166	.13454	-1.02159	-.45841	-5.500	19	.000

Table 7 presents results of paired samples t-test on effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. The result show: $t(19) = -5.50, p < .001$. The result implies that there is a significant difference in means between pre-test and post-test on goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education. The result implies that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy has significant effect on goal-setting among probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy has no significant effect on the goal-setting of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State is rejected.

Hypothesis four: Cognitive Behavioral Therapy has no significant effect on the self-Acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State.

Table 8: Paired Sample t-test on Effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on Self-acceptance of Probating Students of Colleges of Education in Taraba State

	Paired Differences							Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	Df	
				Lower	Upper			
Pretest – Posttest	-.75250	.67852	.15172	-1.07006	-.43494	-4.960	19	.000

Table 8 presents results of paired samples t-test on effect of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. The result show: $t(19) = -4.960, p < .001$.

960, $p < .001$. The result implies that there is a significant difference in means between pre-test and post-test on self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education. The result implies that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy has significant effect on self-acceptance among probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that Cognitive Behavioral Therapy has no significant effect on the self-acceptance of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba State is rejected.

DISCUSSIONS

The findings is in agreement with that of Edom (2023) who carried out a study on the Effects of Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy and Cognitive Behavioural Therapy in Test Anxiety and Academic Achievement among Secondary School Students in Rivers State, and found that that there is much hope for test-anxious students by those that received Rational Emotive Behavioural Therapy and Cognitive Behavioural Therapy.

The findings of the study support that of Yazdizadeh (2023) who conducted a study on the Effectiveness of Rational Emotive Behavioral Therapy in Academic Self-handicapping and Academic Engagement of Students Edo state Nigeria.

The finding of this study is in agreement with the findings of A study by Akomolafe, (2018) aimed to investigate the effectiveness of rational emotive therapy (RET) on the academic performance of probationary students in a Nigerian college of education. The findings of the study showed that there was a significant difference in the academic performance of the experimental group compared to the control group. Specifically, the results revealed that the experimental group performed better than the control group in all the three domains of academic performance tested (cognitive, affective and psychomotor).

The findings of this study is not contrary to the findings of Awujo and Margaret (2018) who carried out a study on the Effects of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on Improving Poor Study Habit among Students in Obioakpo, Rivers State, Nigeria. Results revealed that REBT had significant effect in improving poor study habit among students in the experimental group while the placebo had no effect on study habit of students, the control group did not show any improvement when compared to the REBT experimental group.

The findings of this study is in support of Olusakin (2018) conducted research on the Effect of Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy on the Level of General and Examination Anxieties among Students. The result showed a statically significant difference in favour of the experimental group. The counselling implications were highlighted.

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined that the effects of Rational Emotive Behaviour and Cognitive Behavioral Therapies on self-esteem of probating students of colleges of education in Taraba state. Based on the outcome of the data analysis the study concluded that Rational Emotive Behaviour and Cognitive Behavioral Therapies are effective in improving self-esteem of probating students of colleges of education. However, Rational Emotive Behaviour is more efficacious than Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) in improving self-esteem of probating students of colleges of education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. College Counsellors should adopt Cognitive Behavioural Therapy to help probating students understand the influence of thoughts and feelings on their self-esteem and human behaviour.
2. The college managements should organize a workshop seminar by inviting all students in order to sensitized them on how to enhance their self –esteem.
3. College Counsellors should promotes actions that reinforce positive self-beliefs, like setting achievable goals and celebrating accomplishments among college students.

4. Rational Emotive Behaviour Therapy (REBT) technique should be used by college counselors to effectively address low self-esteem among probating students by targeting irrational thoughts and promoting positive self-evaluation.

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